

IIm-e-Khshnoom

also known as “Parsi IIm-e-Khshnoom”, “Ilme Kṣnum”, “Zoroastrian IIm-e-Khshnoom”, “Khshnoomic (attribute to IIm-e-Khshnoom) teachings”, “Khshnoomists ('followers of IIm-e-Khshnoom')”

By Mariano Errichiello, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg

Entry tags: Religious Group, Zoroastrianism, Parsis (India)

IIm-e-Khshnoom 'Science of Bliss' refers to the religious group primarily composed by members of the Zoroastrian diaspora currently settled in India (henceforth Parsis). They follow the system of beliefs (also named IIm-e-Khshnoom) introduced by Behramshah Naoroji Shroff (1858-1927) at the beginning of the 20th century. Shroff's teachings are based upon an esoteric interpretation of the Avesta, which is the collection of sacred Zoroastrian scriptures. IIm-e-Khshnoom emerged from colonial India, when the Westernisation process exposed the religious vulnerability of the Parsi community. The teachings of Shroff are based on a set of universal laws of nature that span from the idea of reincarnation to that of the vibrational power dwelling in the practice of Zoroastrian rituals. Shroff, a Parsi himself, claimed to have been initiated to IIm-e-Khshnoom by the Sāheb Delān 'Master-Hearts', a secluded community of Zoroastrian spiritual masters in Mount Damāvand, Iran. During his stay, he allegedly acquired abilities like telepathy and divination techniques such as astrology. The Parsis who follow IIm-e-Khshnoom nowadays are a small minority of the approximately 50,000 Zoroastrians who live in India, mainly in Mumbai and in some cities of the state of Gujarat. There are not exclusion or inclusion criteria for the membership of this religious group other than being born from a Zoroastrian family. Nevertheless, ethnocentrism characterises not only the adherents of IIm-e-Khshnoom but a large part of the Parsi community, in contrast to another part of the community which promote religious reformism and conversions. Furthermore, the transmission of IIm-e-Khshnoom across generations has occurred through the familiar nucleus. In effect, families continue to exert a durable impact on the religious canons as well as on the communal ideology and responsibility of Parsis. The followers of IIm-e-Khshnoom emphasise a strict observance of the Zoroastrian rituals and adopt particular principles in the ritual practice. These principles remark the importance of addressing precise thoughts while reciting a given portion of the Avesta correctly accompanied by a specific kinetic motion. They also represent distinctive elements of contradistinction of the followers of IIm-e-Khshnoom against the wider Parsi community. Another distinctive element is the adoption of the liturgical calendar. While the Shenshai is the most widespread calendar among the Zoroastrians of India, the adherents of IIm-e-Khshnoom advocate the adoption of the Fasli calendar. From the 1980's, Parsis who follow the teachings of Shroff can be found in US and Canada as well as in Australia.

Date Range: 1907 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Parsis in India

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Gujarat

Currently, the largest communities of Parsis are in the states of Maharashtra (mainly Mumbai and Pune) and Gujarat (mainly Ahmedabad, Navsari, Surat, Udvada and Vadodara).

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chiniwalla, F. S. *Essential Origins of Zoroastrianism*. Bombay: The Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society, 1942.
- Source 2: Mama, N. F. *A Mazdaznan Mystic. Life-sketch of the late Behramshah Navroji Shroff, the 20th Century Exponent of Zarthoshti Elm-e-Khshnoom (i.e. Esotericism of Zoroastrianism)*. Bombay: The Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zarthosthi Radih Society, 1944.
- Source 3: Tavaría, P. N. *A manual of "Khshnoom". The Zoroastrian occult knowledge*. Bombay: The Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1971.

Notes: The literary production on Ilm-e-Khshnoom consists of more than 100 books and several thousands of articles published in Khshnoomist magazines such as *Frasho-Gard* (1911-1942), *Parsi Avaz* (1947-1974), *Dini Avaz* (1976-2000), *Parsi Pukar* (1995-2008), *Frashogard* (2005-2006), *The Parsee Voice* (2003-2014 - 2016-), *Parsi Avaz* (2008-). The largest part of this literature is composed in Gujarati.

- Source 1: Boyce, M. *Zoroastrians. Their Religious Beliefs and Practices*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd, 1979.
- Source 2: Hinnells, J. R. "Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji." In *Who's Who of World Religions*. London and Basingstoke: The Macmillan Press, 1993.
- Source 3: Hintze, A. "Zoroastrianism." In *Encyclopedia of New Religions. New Religious Movements, Sects and Alternative Spiritualities*. Oxford: Lion Publishing, 2004.

Notes: Ilm-e-Khshnoom is an unexplored subject in scholarship. The assumptions on Ilm-e-Khshnoom contained in the secondary sources are based on some of the available English sources and on scattered insights from research participants. Nevertheless, the sources in Gujarati have never been examined nor translated into a European language.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://frashogard.com/>
- Source 1 Description: This blog started in 2007 to replace the printed magazine *Frashogard* (2005-2006). It is managed by Ervad Marzban J. Hathiram.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ilm-e-khshnoom.blogspot.com/>
- Source 2 Description: This blog was started by Firdosh K. Sukhia in 2010 and ran for 6 years.
- Source 3 URL: <http://mazorcol.org/>
- Source 3 Description: This is the website of the Zoroastrian College, an institute run by Dr. Meher Master-Moos for the propagation of Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.frashogard.com/ilm-e-khshnoom-skydrive/>
- Source 1 Description: This section of the blog *Frashogard* contains a large number of digital copies of Khshnoomist writings with their description.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The followers of IIm-e-Khshnoom are part of the wider Parsi community in India. This community is composed by groups whose differentiation is characterised by diverse interpretations of the Avesta and contrasting communal views. Among these groups, IIm-e-Khshnoom is considered one of the most orthodox. There is a competitive contact with Pundolism whose followers advocate similar beliefs but hold Khshnoomists as a hoax.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although the approach on some delicate communal controversies can be conflictive (i.e. exogamy, conversions, Navjote for children whose parents aren't both Zoroastrian, use of dhokma 'Tower of Silence' for the disposal of corpse, organ donation, renovation of temples which implies the shifting of fire).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The religious affiliation to IIm-e-Khshnoom is not different from that required for Zoroastrianism. It is necessary to be born in a Zoroastrian family and to undergo the Navjote ceremony, which is the ritual of induction into the religion. Recently, there is more flexibility among Parsi Zoroastrians about the performance of Navjote ceremony for children whose mother is non-Zoroastrian. Nevertheless, Khshnoomists firmly condemn this approach.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Being born from Zoroastrian parents.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: A Parsi decides to follow Ilm-e-Khshnoom by personal choice. Families are a significant factors in the transmission of Khshnoomic teachings as they are often imparted from parent to child.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Parsis who don't undergo the Navjote ceremony aren't considered Zoroastrians.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: By strongly advocating ethnocentrism, Khshnoomists are against conversions. As a consequence, their target community is composed by Parsis. Together with a constant media (printed and online) presence, they run periodical talks to build awareness within the wider Parsi community about their beliefs and liturgical approach. This allows Ilm-e-Khshnoom to increase their base of followers.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is not a formal apostasy, the followers of Ilm-e-Khshnoom adopt a form of social ostracism for Zoroastrians (either male or female) who marry outside the fold (marrying a non-

Zoroastrian) or follow other religions.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: According to Khshnoomists, Parsi Zoroastrians who marry outside the fold can't define themselves as Zoroastrian anymore. Their children should not undergo the Navjote ceremony. The same kind of ostracism is towards Parsi Zoroastrians who follow other religions.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, being born as a Zoroastrian represents the last step in the evolution of one's own soul. By disobeying religious canons, the soul doesn't complete the purification process from Evil and will need to re-birth.

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Notes: This number is based upon data collected through participant observation and interviews during the ethnographic fieldwork which I conducted between 2019 and 2020. There isn't an official demographic study on Khshnoomists.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.6

Notes: Khshnoomists probably represent the 0.6% of the total Parsi population. (57,264 according to the census of 2011). Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India "C-01 Appendix : Details of Religious Community Shown Under 'Other Religions And Persuasions' In Main Table C-1- 2011 (India & States/UTs)".

<http://www.censusindia.gov.in/2011census/C-series/C-05/DDW-0000C-05.xlsx> (accessed on the 1st of November of 2018).

Reference: Ministry of Home Affairs Government of India. "'C-01 Appendix : Details of Religious Community Shown Under 'other Religions and Persuasions' in Main Table C-1- 2011 (india & States/uts)". Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, n.d..

<http://www.censusindia.gov.in/2011census/C-series/C-05/DDW-0000C-05.xlsx>.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Despite the followers of Ilm-e-Khshnoom have cosmological and eschatological beliefs which are in contrast with the wider Parsi Zoroastrian population (i.e. the presence of a divine entity above the supreme Lord Ahura Mazda, the concept of reincarnation, a cyclical view of time), they are still ethnically related to the large Parsi community.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Shroff, the Masani and Chiniwalla brothers are all considered leaders in the start and development of Ilm-e-Khehnoom. In most recent times, Kaikhushru Navroji Dastoor (1927-2019) and Adi Furrokh Doctor (1937-2014) have been distinguished Khshnoomists. Currently, Hanoz Mistree and Rita Doctor (sister of Adi) are editing The Parsee Voice, an organ of information on Ilm-e-Khshnoom. Ervad Marzban J. Hathiram is considered an authoritative and knowledgeable figure on Ilm-e-Khshnoom together with Aspi Tavadia. Meher Master-Moos is considered a leader from the most liberal/universalist faction of Khshnoomists.

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: There is no formal organisational structure which appoints/defines leadership. Rather, leadership is based upon personal initiative, good communication skills and knowledge of the subject.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Only one of them believe to possess supernatural powers: Meher Master-Moos. Her small group of followers supports this idea. Master-Moos claims to be in spiritual touch with Shah Behram Varjavand (upcoming saviour who will unite all the world's religious under his leadership). She holds that her actions are the result of instructions received by Shah Behram Varjavand. Nevertheless, the largest part of the Khshnoomic community doesn't believe in her powers and holds that only Shroff had supernatural powers. Furthermore, they consider the use that Master-Moos does of Ilm-e-Khshnoom heretical as she advocates universalist beliefs by promoting conversions, among other things.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Master-Moos, powers are transmitted by Shah Behram Varjavand

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Leaders are not chose formally, rather the consensus of the Khshnoomic community on the leaders' work of dissemination of Ilm-e-Khshnoom (talks, writings) influences a popular acceptance which endows authority.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: Followers can accuse their leaders and keep them accountable.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of the community can accuse other leaders and keep them accountable.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: The leaders are questioned and the Khshnoomic community occasionally faces debates on communal matters.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The collection of sacred scriptures for Khshnoomists as well as for the wider Parsi community is the Avesta. Nevertheless, the interpretation of the Avesta provided by Khshnoomists is quite different from that of the wider community. Furthermore, Khshnoomists also hold with particular reverence some of the writings of Shroff as well as those of Framroze Sorabji Chiniwalla, a direct disciple of Shroff.

Reference: Toledo, Miguel A.. “Primary Sources: Avestan and Pahlavi”. In *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The Avesta, whose oldest composition dates back to the 2nd millennium BC, has been transmitted orally until the Sasanian period (224–651 CE), when it has been codified. The oldest surviving manuscript (K1) is dated 1323 CE. Oral tradition is a constituent characteristic of

Zoroastrianism and ritual performance has been orally transmitted along the centuries. Although the system of beliefs associated with Ilm-e-Khshnoom has been completely codified by Shroff and his disciples, its provenance is partly oral. In effect, when in Iran, Shroff underwent a series of training techniques as part of his initiation, including oral transmission.

Reference: Mama, Nanabhay F.. A Mazdaznan Mystic. Life-sketch of the Late Behramshah Navroji Shroff, the 20th Century Exponent of Zarthoshti Elm-e-khshnoom (i.e. Esotericism of Zoroastrianism). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zarthoshti Radih Society, 1944.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The followers of Ilm-e-Khshnoom maintain that the whole Avesta is considered to be the utterance of the Yazata (divine entity) Zarathustra whose knowledge was directly revealed by Ahura Mazda through seven conferences within 10 years.

Reference: Dastoor, K. N.. Zarathushtra, the Yazata and "life-story" of His Human Form. Bombay: Megha Enterprises, 1984.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists hold that Shroff's writings are based on the initiation he underwent in Iran by the Sāheb Delān, highly evolved Zoroastrians with supernatural powers. For instance, a mean of knowledge transmission was called Sezda, a sort of spiritual trans.

Reference: Mama, Nanabhay F.. A Mazdaznan Mystic. Life-sketch of the Late Behramshah Navroji Shroff, the 20th Century Exponent of Zarthoshti Elm-e-khshnoom (i.e. Esotericism of Zoroastrianism). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zarthoshti Radih Society, 1944.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Avesta is a liturgical corpus and portions of it are recited during the Zoroastrian liturgy. Parsis who want to become priests may undergo a training at the Dadar Athornan Institute, a boarding school, which is the last remaining institute for priestly education. The alternative, is to be trained by other priests. As Parsis can become priests only if male and proceeding from a priestly family, it is common that a father trains his child. At the moment, there is not a specific Khshnoomic training method for priests, nevertheless, there are some Parsi priests who are Khshnoomists and transmit their interpretation of the Avesta through books, articles and talks.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Ilm-e-Khshnoom proposes a different interpretation (also translation) of the Avesta rather than a different set of scriptures. In this framework, the Khshnoomic texts which may be regarded as a codified canon is the Khordeh Avesta 'Small Avesta' by Shroff (and a later version by F. S. Chiniwalla). This is a book containing the main prayers to be recited by a Zoroastrian, with a translation into Gujarati and the related Khshnoomic performance instructions (the description of specific thoughts to focus on during the recitation of prayers).

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. *Khurdeh-avastā Bā Tarīkat* ('khordeh Avesta with Canon'). Bombay: Jamaśedjī Naśarvānjī Pītīt Pārsī Orphanej Kupaṭan Pritiṃg Varks, 1918.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "Celebrating the Salgreh of Our Padshah Sahebs". *frashogard.com*, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/celebrating-the-salgreh-of-our-padshah-sahebs/>.

Reference: Ghosh, Madhushree. "Mumbai's Parsi Fire Temples". *atlasobscura.com*, n.d.. <https://www.atlasobscura.com/places/parsi-fire-temple>.

Reference: Nambiar, Sridevi. "A Brief History of Mumbai's Oldest Surviving Zoroastrian Fire Temple". *theculturetrip.com*, n.d.. <https://theculturetrip.com/asia/india/articles/a-brief-history-of-mumbais-oldest-surviving-zoroastrian-fire-temple/>.

Reference: Eduljee, K. E.. "Pilgrimage Sites". heritageinstitute.com, n.d..
<http://www.heritageinstitute.com/zoroastrianism/worship/udvada.htm>.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Zoroastrian temples in India are built in urban or rural areas which are not of exclusive domain of Parsis.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the size of some fire temples is known, a comparison by size can't be found.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: While there could be some cemetery dedicated to Parsis, Khshnoomists strictly advocate the use of dokhma 'Tower of Silence,' a circular structure for corpses disposal (exposing dead bodies for excarnation operated by vultures).

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Fire temples constitute the main Zoroastrian religious space where liturgy is celebrated. Fire temples are ranked on the grade of the fire which they host. There are three categories: Atash Dadgah, Atash Adaran and Atash Behram, the latter being the most sacred one. In India there are 167 fire temples, of which 8 are Atash Behram. There are no Khshnoomic fire temples as such. All Zoroastrians are allowed in any fire temple, despite their religious affiliation.

Reference: Choksy, Jamsheed K.. "Religious Sites and Physical Structures". In *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Another religious site among the Parsis, including the Khshnoomists, is the Bhika Behram Well in Cross Maida, Mumbai, which is associated with miraculous cure.

Reference: Choksy, Jamsheed K.. "Religious Sites and Physical Structures". In *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "The Importance of Wells and Well Water in Zoroastrianism". *frashogard.com*, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/the-importance-of-wells-and-well-water-in-zoroastrianism/>.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Although Khshnoomists are reluctant to hold icons, the most common religious icons which may found in their houses are: 1. the Faravahar which depicts a winged figure; 2. the image of Zarathustra; 3. images of prominent figures in Zoroastrianism such as the priest Jamshedji Sorab Kukadaru or the legendary king Kay Lohrasp. There are no portrait or photograph of Shroff. Khshnoomsits firmly condemn icons associated divinities or spiritual masters belonging to other religions, as it is the case of Sai Shirdi Baba, whose image is easy to find in Parsi houses. Among Khshnoomists, Master-Moos who advocates a universalist approach, hold icons of Sai Shirdi Baba and Hindu divinities in her Zoroastrian College.

Reference: Yazdi. "THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FARAVAHAR / FAROHAR FIGURE". *zoroastrians.net*, n.d.. <https://zoroastrians.net/2015/07/28/the-significance-of-the-faravahar-farohar-figure/>.

Reference: Eduljee, K. E.. "Zarathushtra Zoroaester". heritageinstitute.com, n.d..
<http://www.heritageinstitute.com/zoroastrianism/zarathushtra/index.htm>.

Reference: Eduljee, K. E.. "ZOROASTER ZARATHUSHTRA ZARATHUSTRA". zoroaster-zarathushtra.blogspot.com, n.d..
<http://zoroaster-zarathushtra.blogspot.com/2011/10/images-of-zarathushtra-zarathustra.html>.

Reference: Anonymous. "Shah Lohrasp and Zarathustra". arshad.wordpress.com, n.d..
<https://arshad.wordpress.com/english/notes-5/shah-lohrasp-and-zarathustra/>.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: These are the fire temples and dokhmas 'Towers of Silence.'

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Fire temples are built according to specific features, including orientation according to cardinal directions. Furthermore, the presence of a well is necessary to access to water used for ritual purposes.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimages include travels to the Zoroastrian motherland, Iran, and visits to the main sacred Zoroastrian places, as well as visits to the highest ranked fire temples (Atash Behram) in India in a single journey.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, each individual is formed by three bodies which are, in turn, three-folded. The physical body is composed by Gaetha (vital organs), Tanu (outer body and skeleton) and Azdebish (oily skeleton); the ultra-physical body is composed by Ushtan (life-energy), Kehrp (subtle body), Tewishi (desire-forces); the divine body is composed by Baod (perfect divine knowledge), Urvan (soul) and Fravashi (sublimest constituent).

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. “The Wondrous Circle of Life – Part 1”. Frashogard, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/the-wondrous-circle-of-life-part-1/>.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The fourth day after the funeral, the dead's soul departs towards the Chinvat Bridge (located in Nisti or mortal cosmos) which separated the physical and spiritual worlds. Depending on how the earthly life has been lived and the extent to what the religious canons have been followed, the soul can return to the physical world and take a re-birth or can start the journey which will end into Hasti (immortal cosmos).

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. “Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation”. Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The specified realm of space is defined by the concept of densification. The

physical world is considered "gross" in terms of density while the spiritual world is subtle. Highest is the realm, the subtler it becomes.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "The Wondrous Circle of Life – Part 5". Frashogard, n.d..
<https://www.frashogard.com/the-wondrous-circle-of-life-part-5/>.

↳ In a human form:
– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:
– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):
– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation is considered as an evolutionary step of the human soul. The successful evolution is linked to the practical adherence to the canons of the religion which the individual is born in.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Corpses are treated in the Dokhma 'Tower of Silence.' Khshnoomists maintain that this system has been developed 9,000 years ago and is the most effective sanitary-wise. The Dokhma counts on an articulate structure to avoid contacts between livings and dead bodies in order to avoid any contagion. Sachkar and Geh Sarna prayers have to be performed before the corpses are consigned to a Dokhma: these rituals are necessary to reduce and limit the impurity of the dead body. The function of the Dokhma is to transform the physical cells of the body into their spiritual state. The combined solar energies disinfect and disintegrate the body without polluting the 4 elements (earth, water, air, fire). Then, vultures take around a hour to excarnate the body and no smell or source of disease is left behind. Dokhmas are built with stones and iron, this is to avoid the spreading of impurity. Inside the Dokhmas, corpses lay on a stone to avoid contact with the earth.

Reference: Chiniwalla, Framroze S.. *Dokhmānī Bulaṃd Jarthoštī Talesam: Sāyaṅṭīphīk Ane Itihāsīk Madehanajarthī Teno Ukel* ('the Sublime Zoroastrian Talisman of Dokhma: Its Understanding from the Scientific and Historical View'). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian & Temperance Society, 1939.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Cremation is condemned from Khshnoomists as the fire is considered a holy element and the dead body is considered polluted.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

Notes: Khshnoomists and Parsi Zoroastrians consider a dead body to be polluted, hence, the disposal of the corpse has to avoid contamination of any other element, including earth.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: The corpses are exposed to sun and vultures atop of a tower in a structure called dokhma 'Tower of silence.'

Notes: Khshnoomists believe that a dead corpse produces a kind of putridity (nasu) that is plenty of microbes.

Reference: Tavaría, Pheroz N.. A Manual of "khshnoom". The Zoroastrian Occult Knowledge. Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1971.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Shroff introduced the figure of Ahu as supreme deity whose emanation is Ahura Mazda. Ahu is not conceivable by human beings and is also indicated as nur ul anavār 'Light of Lights.'

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - No
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Ahu, the supreme deity, is unspeakable, unknowable and unthinkable. The Khshnoomic cosmogony is emanationist and Ahu operates through other divine entities.
 - Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This world is created as a tool to advance inherent purification of Evil. It is created by Ahura Mazda who is omniscient and is emanation of the supreme deity Ahu.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Being omniscient, the supreme god's knowledge has not restrictions.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity has knowledge of the whole creation.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The material creation has been generated as result of the capacity of foreseeing the future. The supreme deity knows that the purification of inherent Evil will successfully happen until the end of times.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: The concept of knowledge ascribed to Ahu goes beyond the concept of knowledge as understood by humans.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Khshnoomic cosmology is emanationist, therefore, the supreme deity acts through a hierarchy of divine entities.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Ahu acts through Ahura Mazda which in turn acts through the Amesha Spentas and Yazatas.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists recite prayers in honour of many Yazatas (divine entities). An example is the Yashts which are a collection of 21 hymns associated with divine entities.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. *Khurdeh-avastā Bā Tarīkat* ('khordeh Avesta with Canon'). Bombay: Jamaśedjī Naśarvānjī Pītīt Pārsī Orphanej Kapaṭan Pritīṃg Varks, 1918.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are called Fravashis and prayers are recited for the Fravashis of the

departed ones. In particular, there is a specific ceremony called Muktdad to help the Fravashis to advance.

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "What to Do and Pray During Muktdad - Part 1". Frashogard, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/what-to-do-and-pray-during-the-muktdad-part-1/>.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Apart of Ahu and his emanation Ahura Mazda, Khshnoomists believe in the Amesha Spentas (divine entities which are closer to Ahura Mazda) and the Yazatas (divine entities).

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Among the various Yazatas (divine entities), Khshnoomists consider Sarosh to be the Yazata in charge of the universe and of the evolution of the humankind.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. Saroś Yajadnuṃ Kudarātñī Tamām Pedāyaśmāṃ Mhān Kāry ('the Great Work of the Yazata Saroś in the Entire Creation'). Bombay: Daphtar Āśakārā Pres, 1915.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Yazatas (divine entities) have specific responsibilities within the creation and human affairs. Generally, their role is to help the creation to purify itself from Evil.

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Among others, the Yazata Sarosh can see the soul of humans in order to help their purification from Evil.

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They can inspire actions of human being by means of several kinds of interactions (dream, thoughts, etc.) as reported by research participants during fieldwork.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings such as the souls of humans can experience joy and happiness after death.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings such as the souls of humans can experience misery and sorrow after death.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, Shroff was initiated by a group of advanced Zoroastrian masters called Saheb Delan, who can decide to assume a human form if necessary.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: They can assume human forms when they want to enter in physical contact with some evolved human being, like the case of Shroff.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: They can assume human forms when they want to enter in physical contact with some evolved human being, like the case of Shroff. Otherwise, they can be invisible to human eyes.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. A Wondrous Life. The True Story of the Master Ustad Saheb Behramshah Nowroji Shroff. Mumbai: Marzban J. Hathiram, 2013.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They can interfere with the life of selected individuals like the case of the initiation of Shroff. They attracted Shroff to their secluded community in Iran and trained him.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: They can reward by making themselves visible and providing spiritual knowledge.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists maintain that Āzar Kayvān, a Persian mystic of the 16th and 17th centuries, was a member of the secluded community of the Saheb Delan. Against the advice of his superiors, he left the community to spread the Zoroastrian spiritual message. Nevertheless, when he realised that it was a mistake, he wasn't granted access back to the community.

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "Hazrat Dastur Azar Kaiwan: How Ilm-e-khshnoom Answers the Riddles About the Life and Times of a Great Zarathushtrian Saint". Frashogard 1, no. 1 (January 1, 2007).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They have supernatural powers like telepathy.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through other individuals who serve as emissaries. These emissaries can be unaware of their task.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Ahu is the supreme divine entity and Ahura Mazda its emanation. The Amesha Spentas are next in the hierarchy, then all the other Yazatas come.

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Each Amesha Spenta and Yazata has a specific function and task to carry, either in Hasti (immortal cosmos) or Nisti (mortal cosmos).

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: A specific divine entity is associated with each day of the calendar. Khshnoomists believe that the Fasli calendar is the most authentic one.

Reference: Chiniwalla, Framroze S.. *Fasalī Ātaś-kadeh Tathā Phasalī Ālāt Banāvānī Nāpāyadār Hīlacāl* ('unfounded Movement of Fooling Fasli Atash Kadeh and Fasli Implements'). Mumbai: Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1940.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, supernatural beings interact with souls and, within the range of their roles and functions, they generally support Ahura Mazda in the work of purifying Evil and transforming it into Good, resulting in leading the creation towards the state of "perfection." One of the supernatural beings who is closer to human souls, the Yazata Sarosh, has powers called Aoj (power to perform tasks to lead human souls to perfection) and Taji (power of purification of souls). While there is no reference to any supernatural active monitoring of specific human behaviours associated with social norms, the Khshnoomic eschatology provides a system of reward and punishment in accordance to the way the human experience has been conducted. In effect, the human beings have free will to choose righteousness or deceit in their life. The eschatological figure of Kerdar (form or phantom body) is introduced and represents the accumulation of thoughts, words and deeds performed by a human during her/his lifetime. The Kerdar serves as a way to monitor how the life of a human has been lived and post-mortem rewards or punishments are associated with it.

Reference: Tavaria, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: When a human dies, a feminine form or phantom body called Kerdar is produced after the fourth day after death. If the human has committed sins during her/his lifetime, the relative Kerdar will appear as a ugly witch and will be too "gross" to cross the Chinvat Bridge (connection with superior levels of existence) and will have to go through re-birth.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: When a human dies, a feminine form or phantom body called Kerdar is produced after the fourth day after death. If the human has lived in accordance with the religious precepts during her/his lifetime, the relative Kerdar will appear as a beautiful maiden and will be able to cross the Chinvat Bridge and pass to the next level of existence without going through re-birth.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: There are different views on Shah Behram Varjavand (the coming saviour). Some Khshnoomists say he is supposed to reveal himself this year, others don't know. They all agree that he is already born.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Reference: Gotlaseth, Cawas P.. Šāḥ Beherām Varajāvaṃd ('shah Behram Varzavand'). Mumbai: Stets Pipal Press, 1978.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: Shah Behram Varjavand will unite all religions under his leadership.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Shah Behram Varjavand will resurrect Zoroastrianism to its past glory.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomist eschatology can be resumed by the "Law of Compensative Retribution and Universal Adjustment" introduced by Shroff in his writings. According to this law, when a soul incarnates in a human form, it carries obligations generated towards other worlds (divine, mineral, vegetable, animal, human) in its existence. The purpose of the human soul is to work towards a final settlement of such obligations in order to move back to Hasti (immortal cosmos).

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The end of the world is called Frashogard which is a Gujarati transliteration of the Middle Persian fraš-gird proceeding from the Av. frašō.kərəti 'perfection.' Khshnoomists believe that, in Frashogard, the whole creation and Ahura Mazda will be reunited. According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, time is cyclical (opposed to the mainstream linear one) and is formed by 7 eons which are composed by endless cycles of 81,000 years. At the end of the 7 eons there will be Frashogard.

Reference: Hathiram, Marzban J.. "A Not-so-brief History of Time and the Earth". n.a., n.d..

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The required tasks correspond to the Zoroastrian religious canons to be strictly followed.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

Notes: While the divine judgement occurs in the individual eschatology, where a soul can reincarnate if still needs to purify inner Evil, in universal eschatology the whole creation will unite with Ahura Mazda.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: Frashogard 'perfection' refers to the restoration of the spiritual world which will be totally purified from Evil, making the physical creation not necessary anymore.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: Not in the current human form.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Parsi social norms are deeply rooted in Zoroastrian religion and the differentiation between them and the community's *tarikāt* 'religious canons' is blurred. Nevertheless, norms that may consider social include endogamy and exclusive access to fire temples (non-Zoroastrians can't access). Furthermore, for Khshnoomists is important to cover their head through a *topi* (prayer cap) or a scarf and to wear leather sleepers in order to preserve their *Khoreh* (personal magnetism or aura). For the same reason, Khshnoomists believe that it is important to avoid contact with invisible microbes which are created when taking the bath, partaking of meals, attending nature's calls, cutting hair and nails, spitting, urinating and bleeding. In these cases, respective rituals (i.e. *Kusti*) have to be performed.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the moral norms of Khshnoomists have their origin in the religion.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: The progressive adaptation of communal norms to the present times advocated by a part of the Parsi Zoroastrian community is firmly condemned by Khshnoomists who advocate the importance of preserving the communal norms established by their forefathers.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists associate communal norms such as endogamy with ethnocentric exclusivity. In effect, they emphasise the importance of 'marrying within the fold' as a way to preserve the religion; otherwise, exogamy will dissolve/corrupt the religion.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: An example is the opposition of Khshnoomists to organ donation. The physical and subtle bodies of a Zoroastrian vibrate at a certain level and receiving/giving organs would affect the vibratory power of the body.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, ideally, these norms apply to all Zoroastrians, although not all Zoroastrians follow them.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Parsis are known for their trustworthiness and honesty in business. However, many contemporary Parsis claim that the current community is gradually become more inclined towards corruption.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists promote the expression of one's opinions frankly and publicly, especially when standing for communal positions which may be unpopular.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– No

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Parsis believe that accumulating wealth is not a sin. Rather, it is a blessing and they are known for their philanthropic activities.

Reference: Vevaina, Leilah. "Good Deeds: Parsi Trusts from 'the Womb to the Tomb'". *Modern Asian Studies* 52, no. 1 (January 1, 2018).

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Selfishness is considered a behaviour which impedes the purification from Evil that every human undergoes in the earthly experience.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of righteousness deeply lays in the religious tradition of Parsis. In Avesta, the term *aša-* 'truth, righteousness, order' corresponds to one of the Amesha Spentas 'bounteous immortals,' divine entities emanating from Ahura Mazda. In *Ilm-e-Khshnum*, *aša-* is interpreted as a state of holiness acquired by living a life in accordance with the *tarikāt* 'religious canons.'

Reference: Tavarā, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual purity covers a particular significance for *Khshnumists*. Nowadays, some of the Zoroastrian purity laws are not followed anymore, however, followers of *Ilm-e-Khshnum* staunchly promote it. Furthermore, *Khshnumists* introduce a ritual rationale associated with the vibratory power of the Avestan prayers which, recited in the proper way, have purification effects.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah N.. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of *Ilm-i-khshnum*. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong emphasis of Khshnoomists on the familial obedience. In particular, attempts to reform the religious canons are considered as an offence to the forefathers who, with sacrifice and religious perseverance, built a safe and wealthy community. Being an ethnic community that lacks a central theological authority, families become the main centre of religious transmission.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists consider the lack of loyalty in family life, friendship and business partnership as one of the elements of decay of the Parsi community.

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists believe that excesses are generally harmful and corrupt the souls of individuals.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: Discipline, especially in conducting a life in accordance with the tarikat 'religious canons', is considered an important virtue by Khshnoomists.

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists exhibit an assertive and decisive behaviour, especially when engaging with communal and religious topics, showing no hesitation even for unpopular stands.

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of "hope" in IIm-e-Khshnoom is linked to the belief that Shah Behram Varjavand is soon coming to reestablish order in this period of decay for humanity. Hope in the arrival of this saviour gives to Khshnoomists the motivation to continue following their religious canons.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– No

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists pay particular reverence to their religious divinities as well as to distinguished Zoroastrian figures. A practical representation of this virtue is expressed by the way they revere (talks, Baj ceremonies, publications) prominent Khshnoomists of the past (e.g. Behramshah N. Shroff, the Chiniwalla and Masani brothers, K. N. Dastoor and Adi Doctor, among others).

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Having faith and devotion in Ahura Mazda and other divine entities are central elements in IIm-e-Khshnoom. In particular, there is an emphasis on the preformative aspect of these elements by encouraging Zoroastrians to strictly follow the rituals as prescribed and avoid simplifications.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: Zoroastrian wisdom is held in high regard by Khshnoomists, in particular that transmitted to Shroff by the Sāheb Delān of Mount Damavānd in Iran. In effect, the Sāheb Delān are considered the wisest living men.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Physical purity is important for Khshnoomists. Those who have access to taro (unconsecrated bull's urine), in the morning, pass it through the body before taking a bath as a way of purification from a vibratory point of view.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: According to Ilm-e-Khshnoom, when souls go towards human incarnation they split in male and female counterparts. Hence, Khshnoomists consider homosexual behaviours as unnatural and illegitimate human phenomena which are deviations from the nature of one's own soul. Their view is also supported by scriptures, where it is possible to find references on this topic.

Reference: Skjærvø, Prods Oktor. "HOMOSEXUALITY I. IN ZOROASTRIANISM". *Encyclopædia Iranica*, n.d.. <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/homosexuality-i>.

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Any homosexual behaviour is condemned.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Any homosexual behaviour is condemned.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not prescribed in Zoroastrianism. There is a special care for priests while they perform purification rituals: in those cases, priests wear specific clothes and gloves for meals and eat with a spoon food exclusively cooked by Zoroastrians.

Reference: Modi, Jivanji J.. *The Religious Ceremonies and Customs of the Parsees*. Bombay: Jehangir B. Karani's Sons Book-Sellers & Publishers, 1937.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Ilm-e-Khshnoom advocates orthopraxy, however, there is no a specific requirement other than having gone through the Navjote ceremony.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, Khshnoomists are fervent adherent to their system of beliefs and are strict practitioners. Regarding ethics, the following of their tarikat 'religious canons' is essential.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: The participation in private rituals (i.e. Jashan ceremonies) is not required but preferred.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: The participation in large-scale rituals (i.e. Baj ceremonies for death anniversaries) is not required but preferred.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: An ethnic community.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some Zoroastrian organisations and/or families give support for famine relief, many times anonymously, as form of charity and not necessarily for Zoroastrians. There is no Khshnoomic institution doing so.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are Zoroastrian institutions that support poverty relief (i.e. World Zoroastrian Organisation),

however, there are not Khshnoomic institutions doing so.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are Zoroastrian institutions that provide care for the elder Parsis (i.e. WZO Senior Citizens Centre in Navsari), however, there are not Khshnoomic institutions doing so.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a boarding school for Zoroastrians who want to become priests: Dadar Athornan Institute in Mumbai. There are other communal schools where Zoroastrian subjects are taught. There is no institution providing formal education on IIm-e-Khshnoom.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although the boarding school for priests is only for males as in India Zoroastrian females can't become priests.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Parsi communal activities are often managed by Anjuman which usually are Trust. Among their activities, there could also be the management of fire temples (e.g. maintenance, salaries of priests, etc.) and of Parsi residential colonies (e.g. Bombay Parsi Panchayet). The Zoroastrian Radih Society was formed by Shroff to establish a Parsi colony which is currently known as Behram Baug, in Mumbai. Later on, the Behramshah Shroff Co-operative Housing Society Ltd took on the management of this colony.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This refers to the institutions of the Government of India.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The Gujarati version adopted by Parsis is a dialect known as Parsi Gujarati. Parsis in Mumbai are fluent in English and speak (not all of them can read and write) in Gujarati. Parsis in Gujarat are fluent in Gujarati and many of them speak/write/read in English, depending on the level of education. Apart of English and Parsi Gujarati, Khshnoomists use technical terms called logato which are a distinctive mark of Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and Gujarati through formal education.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Khshnoomists advocate the use of the Fasli calendar, however, there is only one fire temple in

Mumbai following such calendar (Petit Fasli Agiary) and is not associated with Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The most widespread calendar is the Shenshai. The second in use is the Kadimi calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "The Wondrous Circle of Life - Part 5". Frashogard, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/the-wondrous-circle-of-life-part-5/>.

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "The Wondrous Circle of Life - Part 1". Frashogard, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/the-wondrous-circle-of-life-part-1/>.

Reference: Yes [specify]: The corpses are exposed to sun and vultures atop of a tower in a structure called dokhma 'Tower of silence.', Tavaría, Pheroz N.. A Manual of "khshnoom". The Zoroastrian Occult Knowledge. Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1971.

Reference: Yes, Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māte Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911. , ,

Reference: Yes, Shroff, Behramshah N.. Khurdeh-avastā Bā Tarīkat ('khordeh Avesta with Canon'). Bombay:

Jamašedjī Našarvānjī Pītīt Pārsī Orphanej Kapaṭan Pritīṅg Varks, 1918. ,

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "What to Do and Pray During Muktaḍ - Part 1". Frashogard, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/what-to-do-and-pray-during-the-muktaḍ-part-1/>.

Reference: Yes, Shroff, Behramshah N.. Saroš Yajadnuṃ Kudaratnī Tamām Pedāyašmām Mhān Kāry ('the Great Work of the Yazata Saroš in the Entire Creation'). Bombay: Daphtar Āšakārā Pres, 1915.

Reference: Yes, Tavaría, Phiroz N.. "Zoroastrianism and the Doctrine of Re-incarnation". Bombay: Unpublished, 1956. , , , , , , ,

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. A Wondrous Life. The True Story of the Master Ustad Saheb Behramshah Nowroji Shroff. Mumbai: Marzban J. Hathiram, 2013.

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "Hazrat Dastur Azar Kaiwan: How Ilm-e-khshnoom Answers the Riddles About the Life and Times of a Great Zarathushtrian Saint". Frashogard 1, no. 1 (January 1, 2007).

Reference: Yes [specify]: A specific divine entity is associated with each day of the calendar. Khshnoomists believe that the Fasli calendar is the most authentic one., Chiniwalla, Framroze S.. Fasalī Ātaš-kadeh Tathā Phasalī Ālāt Banāvvanī Nāpāyadār Hīlacāl ('unfounded Movement of Fooling Fasli Atash Kadeh and Fasli Implements'). Mumbai: Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1940.

Reference: Yes, Gotlaseth, Cawas P.. Šāḥ Beherām Varajāvaṃḍ ('shah Behram Varzavand'). Mumbai: Stets Pipal Press, 1978.

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "A Not-so-brief History of Time and the Earth". n.a., n.d..

Reference: Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.6, Ministry of Home Affairs Government of India. "'C-01 Appendix : Details of Religious Community Shown Under 'other Religions and Persuasions' in Main Table C-1- 2011 (india & States/uts)'"'. Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, n.d.. <http://www.censusindia.gov.in/2011census/C-series/C-05/DDW-0000C-05.xlsx>.

Reference: Yes, Toledo, Miguel A.. "Primary Sources: Avestan and Pahlavi". In The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

Reference: Yes, Mama, Nanabhay F.. A Mazdaznan Mystic. Life-sketch of the Late Behramshah Navroji Shroff, the 20th Century Exponent of Zarthoshti Elm-e-khshnoom (i.e. Esotericism of Zoroastrianism). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zarthoshti Radih Society, 1944.

Reference: Yes, Mama, Nanabhay F.. A Mazdaznan Mystic. Life-sketch of the Late Behramshah Navroji Shroff, the 20th Century Exponent of Zarthoshti Elm-e-khshnoom (i.e. Esotericism of Zoroastrianism). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian and Temperance Society and Zarthoshti Radih Society, 1944.

Reference: Yes, Choksy, Jamsheed K.. "Religious Sites and Physical Structures". In The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Another religious site among the Parsis, including the Khshnoomists, is the Bhika Behram Well in Cross Maida, Mumbai, which is associated with miraculous cure., Choksy, Jamsheed K.. "Religious Sites and Physical Structures". In The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2015.

Reference: Yes, Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sāmāj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Yes, Skjærvø, Prods Oktor. "HOMOSEXUALITY I. IN ZOROASTRIANISM". Encyclopædia Iranica, n.d.. <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/homosexuality-i>.

Reference: No, Modi, Jivanji J.. The Religious Ceremonies and Customs of the Parsees. Bombay: Jehangir B. Karani's Sons Book-Sellers & Publishers, 1937.

Reference: Yes, Vevaina, Leilah. "Good Deeds: Parsi Trusts from 'the Womb to the Tomb'". *Modern Asian Studies* 52, no. 1 (January 1, 2018).

Reference: Yes, Shroff, Behramshah N.. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion') - Bird's Eye-view of Ilm-i-khshnum. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Yes, Chiniwalla, Framroze S.. Dokhmānī Bulaṃd Jarthoštī Talesam: Sāyanṭīphīk Ane Itihāsīk Madehanajarthī Teno Ukel ('the Sublime Zoroastrian Talisman of Dokhma: Its Understanding from the Scientific and Historical View'). Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian & Temperance Society, 1939.

Reference: Yes, Yazdi. "THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FARAVAHAR / FAROHAR FIGURE". zoroastrians.net, n.d.. <https://zoroastrians.net/2015/07/28/the-significance-of-the-faravahar-farohar-figure/>.

Reference: Yes, Eduljee, K. E.. "Zarathushtra Zoroaester". heritageinstitute.com, n.d.. <http://www.heritageinstitute.com/zoroastrianism/zarathushtra/index.htm>.

Reference: Yes, Eduljee, K. E.. "ZOROASTER ZARATHUSHTRA ZARATHUSTRA". zoroaster-zarathushtra.blogspot.com, n.d.. <http://zoroaster-zarathushtra.blogspot.com/2011/10/images-of-zarathushtra-zarathustra.html>.

Reference: Yes, Anonymous. "Shah Lohrasp and Zarathustra". arshatad.wordpress.com, n.d.. <https://arshatad.wordpress.com/english/notes-5/shah-lohrasp-and-zarathustra/>.

Reference: Yes, Hathiram, Marzban J.. "Celebrating the Salgreh of Our Padshah Sahebs". frashogard.com, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/celebrating-the-salgreh-of-our-padshah-sahebs/>.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Another religious site among the Parsis, including the Khshnoomists, is the Bhika Behram Well in Cross Maida, Mumbai, which is associated with miraculous cure., Hathiram, Marzban J.. "The Importance of Wells and Well Water in Zoroastrianism". frashogard.com, n.d.. <https://www.frashogard.com/the-importance-of-wells-and-well-water-in-zoroastrianism/>.

Reference: Yes, Ghosh, Madhushree. "Mumbai's Parsi Fire Temples". atlasobscura.com, n.d.. <https://www.atlasobscura.com/places/parsi-fire-temple>.

Reference: Yes, Nambiar, Sridevi. "A Brief History of Mumbai's Oldest Surviving Zoroastrian Fire Temple". theculturetrip.com, n.d.. <https://theculturetrip.com/asia/india/articles/a-brief-history-of-mumbais-oldest-surviving-zoroastrian-fire-temple/>.

Reference: Yes, Eduljee, K. E.. "Pilgrimage Sites". heritageinstitute.com, n.d.. <http://www.heritageinstitute.com/zoroastrianism/worship/udvada.htm>.

Reference: Yes, Dastoor, K. N.. Zarathushtra, the Yazata and "life-story" of His Human Form. Bombay: Megha Enterprises, 1984.